

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/usgs-bison
hash://md5/4ae47cde0b079d256c0b1490bd51d33e

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2026-06-04

Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/usgs-bison, has fingerprint hash://md5/4ae47cde0b079d256c0b1490bd51d33e, is 738MiB in size and contains 220,540 interactions with 8 unique types of associations (e.g., interactsWith) between 12,269 primary taxa (e.g., Lasioglossum) and 13,356 associated taxa (e.g., NULL). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

AMNH Invertebrate Paleontology Collection - Version 1.10
https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=amnh-fi_2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z
 Assessing the impact of pest monitoring traps on *Bombus griseocollis* (Hymenoptera: Apidae) colony growth and development - Version 1.4
https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=colony_2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z
 A survey of bees (Hymenoptera: Apoidea) in the Bear River Mountains in northern Utah - Version 1.10
https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=ars_hip_2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z
 Auburn University Museum of Natural History Fishes Voucher Collections - Version 8.2
https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=aum-fishes_2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z
 Auburn University Museum of Natural History Invertebrates - Version 1.12
https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=aum-inverts_2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z
 Auburn University Museum of Natural History Mollusks - Version 1.6
https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=aum-mollusks_2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z
 Bee Fauna of National Wildlife Refuges in the Pacific Northwest, 2010-2016 - Version 1.3
https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=usda-fws-nwr-beefauna-pacific-nw_2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z
 BMSM Bailey-Matthews National Shell

Museum - Version 1.47 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=bmnsms-shell> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z BRFC Black Rock Forest Consortium Herbarium - Version 1.5 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=brfcherb> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z Carnegie Museum of Natural History - Mollusks (CM-Mollusks) - Version 1.0 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=cmnh-mollusks> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z Carnegie Museum of Natural History - Traub Flea Collection Occurrence Data, Part 1 - Version 1.0 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=cmnh-fleas> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z Characterizing bumble bee (*Bombus*) communities in the United States and assessing a conservation monitoring method - Version 1.2 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=usda-bombus-communities> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z Cornell University Insect Collection (CUIC) - Version 1.6 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=cuic> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z Cumulative effects of climate and landscape structure on *Bombus* assemblages within agricultural fields throughout the U.S. - Version 1.2 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=bombusutah> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z Curtis Rd Biodiversity Survey - Powered by Aneccdata.org - Version 1.1 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=curtis-767> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission - Freshwater Fishes of Florida - 1956-2000 - Version 1.5 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=fwc-floridafreshwaterfishes> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z HBOI Marine Biomedical and Biotechnology Reference Collection (MBRC) - Version 1.4 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=mbrc> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z Invasive Plant Atlas of the MidSouth (IPAMS) - Version 1.4 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=ipams> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z Land-use and climate drive shifts in *Bombus* assemblage composition - Version 1.2 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=landuse> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z LSUM Bernard Lowy Mycological Herbarium at Louisiana State University - Fungi - Version 1.7 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=lsum-fungi> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z LSU Shirley C. Tucker Herbarium at Louisiana State University - Algae - Version 1.10 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=lsu-algae> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z MCNH Museum of Cultural and Natural History Bird Collection - Version 1.0 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=mcnh-bird> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z Mohonk Preserve 3D Specimens: Birds - Version 1.4 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=3d-specimens-birds> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z Mohonk Preserve Herbarium - Version 1.2 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=mohonk-preserve-dsrc-herbarium> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z Mohonk Preserve Historical Observational Index Card Natural History Data - Version 1.8 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=mohonk-index-card> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z MPM Milwaukee Public Museum Invertebrate Zoology Collection - Version 1.7 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=mpm-invert> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z myFOSSIL eMuseum - Version 1.7 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=myfossil> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z Occurance Data from the Revision of the Du-

foureine Genus *Micralictoides* - Version 1.1 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=micralictoides>
 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z Occurrence Data from Revision of the
 Rophitine Genus *Protodufourea* - Version 1.2 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=protodufourea>
 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z Occurrence Dataset from the Re-
 vision of the Subgenus *Osmia* (*Diceratasmia*) - Version 1.6
<https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=diceratasmia> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z
 Oklahoma Vascular Plants Database - Version 1.3 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=okl-herb>
 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z Pollination Biology and Bee Pollina-
 tors of *Grindelia squarossa* - Version 1.1 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=grin>
 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z TEST for oVert - Version 1.16
https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=test_idigbio 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z
 UCDavis - Western USA - Monarch Butterflies - 1892-2005 - Version
 3.1 https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=ucdavis_western_usa_monarchs
 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z UCR University of California Riverside
 Herbarium - Version 1.3 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=ucr-plants>
 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z UTEX Culture Collection of Algae
 at The University of Texas Living Algae Holdings - Version 1.2
<https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=utex> 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z
 Wild bees of Grand Staircase-Escalante National Monument -
 Version 1.9 <https://ipt.gbif.us/archive.do?r=usda-gsenm-inventory>
 2026-06-02T20:08:28.843Z hash://md5/4ae47cde0b079d256c0b1490bd51d33e

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like
 Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer
 (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024)
 combined with third-party tools like `grep`, `mlr`, `tail` and `head`.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.11
nomer	0.6.5
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 738MiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/usgs-bison

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/usgs-bison \
  > review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/usgs-bison \
  > interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/usgs-bison \
  | nomer append col \
  > name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

You can find a copy of the full review script at check-data.sh. See also GitHub and Codeberg.

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

An extensive list of files produced as part of the review process can be found in Appendix A. Review Files.

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/usgs-bison`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/usgs-bison`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/usgs-bison`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/usgs-bison`)

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/usgs-bison`, has fingerprint hash://md5/4ae47cde0b079d256c0b1490bd51d33e, is 738MiB in size and contains 220,540 interactions with 8 unique types of associations (e.g., `interactsWith`) between 12,269 primary taxa (e.g., `Lasioglossum`) and 13,356 associated taxa (e.g., `NULL`).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped `csv`, `tsv`, `geopackage` and `parquet` archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped `html` page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 2: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Phorodon cannabis	interactsWith	Cannabis plant	396e1ef8-a21f-4b0c-aa42-7240e29b278f
Thrips tabaci	interactsWith	Cannabis plant	14054c45-f84e-4ccf-83a2-3b932cb8a973

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Phenacoccus solenopsis	adjacentTo	Coleus sp.	11f8700f-5fd1-4c52-81a4-49aaa82c1498
Pseudococcus	adjacentTo	Schefflera sp.	38b4bd5a-c8ef-410e-bc99-bbef08308304

Table 3: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
interactsWith	199687
adjacentTo	17919
hasHost	2611
eats	127
visitsFlowersOf	113
killedBy	52
endoparasiteOf	30
hostOf	1

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Lasioglossum	13342
Halictus tripartitus	6697
Perdita calloleuca	6413
Ceratina nanula	5427
Apis mellifera	4190
Perdita subfasciata	3860
Agapostemon angelicus / texanus	2786
Perdita zebrata flavens	2666
Bombus fervidus	2471
Perdita	2214
Hylaeus	1995
Perdita similis	1842
Anthophora bomboides	1700
Anthophora urbana	1674
Perdita aridella	1433
Colletes phaceliae	1408

sourceTaxonName	count
Bombus huntii	1270
Bombus impatiens	1217
Perdita festiva	1195

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
NULL	57969
Tamarix sp.	9495
Ericameria nauseosa ssp. nauseosa var. nauseosa	7661
Chrysothamnus sp.	2941
Melilotus alba	2573
Senecio spartioides	2404
Cleome lutea	2324
Gutierrezia sarothrae	2174
Hydrilla verticillata	2081
Melilotus officinalis	1904
Salsola pestifer	1740
Taraxacum officinale	1572
Cirsium sp.	1426
Sphaeralcea grossulariifolia	1399
Psoralea lanceolata	1330
Chrysothamnus viscidiflorus	1325
Erigeron sp.	1267
Chrysothamnus linifolius	1234
Asteraceae sp. (yellow)	1187

Table 6: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
Lasioglossum	interactsWith	NULL	10300
Halictus tripartitus	interactsWith	NULL	3050
Bombus fervidus	interactsWith	NULL	2448
Agapostemon angelicus / texanus	interactsWith	NULL	2343

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
Anthophora bomboides	interactsWith	NULL	1614
Perdita calloleuca	interactsWith	Salsola pestifer	1548
Perdita calloleuca	interactsWith	NULL	1287
Perdita subfasciata	interactsWith	Ericameria nauseosa ssp. nauseosa var. nauseosa	1242
Bombus impatiens	interactsWith	NULL	1208
Perdita zebrata flavens	interactsWith	Cleome lutea	1168
Apis mellifera	interactsWith	Tamarix sp.	1120
Perdita calloleuca	interactsWith	Melilotus alba	1079
Bombus huntii	interactsWith	NULL	1039
Perdita calloleuca	interactsWith	Tamarix sp.	982
Perdita aridella	interactsWith	NULL	914
Perdita zebrata flavens	interactsWith	NULL	888
Agapostemon virescens	interactsWith	NULL	787
Bombus rufocinctus	interactsWith	NULL	762
Bombus griseocollis	interactsWith	NULL	720

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

You can download the indexed dataset under review at indexed-interactions.csv.gz. A tab-separated file can be found at indexed-interactions.tsv.gz

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. download svg

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution. These maps were generated using MapServer (McKenna et al. 2025) tools configured via map configuration indexed-interactions.map :

```
MAP
  SIZE 1600 800
  EXTENT -180 -90 180 90
  PROJECTION
    "init=epsg:4326"
  END
  LAYER # MODIS WMS map from NASA
    NAME "modis_nasa"
    TYPE RASTER
    OFFSITE 0 0 0
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE WMS
    CONNECTION "https://gibs.earthdata.nasa.gov/wms/epsg4326/best/wms.cgi?"

  METADATA
    "wms_srs" "EPSG:4326"
    "wms_name" "OSM_Land_Water_Map"
    "wms_server_version" "1.1.1"
    "wms_format" "image/jpeg"
  END
  CLASS
    STYLE
      COLOR 232 232 232
      OUTLINECOLOR 32 32 32
    END
  END
  LAYER
    NAME "indexed-interactions"
    TYPE POLYGON
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE OGR
    CONNECTION "indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg"
    DATA "indexed-interactions-h3"
    CLASS
      STYLE
        COLORRANGE 253.0 231.0 37.0 32.0 164.0 134.0
        DATARANGE 0.3010299956639812 4.994576683764141
        RANGEITEM "log_number_of_records"
```

```

        OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
      END
    END
  END
END

```


Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at `indexed-interactions.gpkg` for point data and `indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg` for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 7: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Depth	NONE	col	Depth

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Years ago	NONE	col	Years ago
Armillaria mellea	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Armillaria mellea
Septobasidium	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Septobasidium

Table 8: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	8818
col	class	13
col	family	136
col	genus	1229
col	gigaclass	1
col	kingdom	2
col	order	20
col	phylum	2
col	species	10382
col	subclass	2
col	subfamily	2
col	subgenus	35
col	subspecies	377
col	subterclass	1
col	tribe	5
col	variety	82
discoverlife	NA	20149
discoverlife	species	748
gbif	NA	8297
gbif	class	14
gbif	family	138
gbif	form	2
gbif	genus	1243
gbif	kingdom	3
gbif	order	17
gbif	phylum	2
gbif	species	10589
gbif	subspecies	455
gbif	variety	407
itis	NA	12422
itis	class	11
itis	division	1

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
itis	family	134
itis	genus	1022
itis	kingdom	2
itis	order	21
itis	phylum	1
itis	species	6798
itis	subclass	2
itis	subgenus	2
itis	subspecies	349
itis	superclass	1
itis	superorder	2
itis	tribe	1
itis	variety	144
mdd	NA	20896
ncbi	NA	12212
ncbi	clade	2
ncbi	class	12
ncbi	cohort	1
ncbi	family	134
ncbi	genus	1103
ncbi	kingdom	1
ncbi	order	20
ncbi	phylum	1
ncbi	species	7335
ncbi	subclass	2
ncbi	subgenus	18
ncbi	subspecies	58
ncbi	superclass	1
ncbi	superorder	1
ncbi	varietas	15
pdb	NA	18901
pdb	class	14
pdb	family	133
pdb	genus	566
pdb	informal	1
pdb	infraclass	1
pdb	kingdom	2
pdb	order	24
pdb	phylum	2
pdb	species	1248
pdb	subclass	3
pdb	subfamily	1
pdb	subgenus	1
pdb	suborder	1

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
pbdb	superclass	1
pbdb	tribe	1
pbdb	unranked clade	5
tpt	NA	20414
tpt	family	18
tpt	genus	91
tpt	order	2
tpt	species	371
wfo	NA	15609
wfo	family	33
wfo	genus	638
wfo	phylum	1
wfo	species	4536
wfo	subspecies	65
wfo	variety	64
worms	NA	14773
worms	class	16
worms	family	120
worms	forma	1
worms	genus	677
worms	gigaclass	1
worms	kingdom	2
worms	order	19
worms	phylum	1
worms	phylum (division)	1
worms	species	5172
worms	subclass	2
worms	subgenus	1
worms	suborder	1
worms	subspecies	117
worms	subterclass	1
worms	variety	25

Table 9: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	NONE	10655
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	15003
col	SYNONYM_OF	6458
discoverlife	NONE	25883
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1052
discoverlife	SYNONYM_OF	448
discoverlife	HOMONYM_OF	40
gbif	NONE	10111
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	17431
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	7585
itis	NONE	14432
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	11565
itis	SYNONYM_OF	1426
mdd	NONE	26824
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	120
mdd	SYNONYM_OF	2
ncbi	NONE	14393
ncbi	SAME_AS	11953
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	870
ncbi	COMMON_NAME_OF	14
pbdb	NONE	23617
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	3200
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	1263
tpt	NONE	26456
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	548
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	52
wfo	NONE	18620
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	672
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	7259
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	1966
worms	NONE	18854
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	7645
worms	SYNONYM_OF	1392

Table 10: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 11: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-04T00:36:56Z	summary	https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/usgs-bison/archive/fe725b47efdd9d42851fda0d0fbf935eada04
2026-06-04T00:36:56Z	summary	220540 interaction(s)
2026-06-04T00:36:56Z	summary	0 note(s)
2026-06-04T00:36:56Z	summary	390 info(s)

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-06-04) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

Appendix A. Review Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: “Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike.”

filename	description
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map

filename	description
indexed-interactions.map	mapserver configuration to plot species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads

filename	description
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

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